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1 **Knocking-out the brassinosteroid biosynthesis genes *DWARF1* or**
2 ***DWARF4* produces upright canopy architecture in wheat**

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13 **Abstract**

14 **Background:** Brassinosteroids (BR) regulate multiple agronomic traits in plants, including
15 leaf angle. BR depletion promotes an upright canopy architecture, which can improve vertical
16 light distribution and grain yields in cereals under high planting densities. However, broad
17 reductions in BR activity often have negative impacts on fertility and grain size. Spatially
18 restricted modification of BR metabolism through targeting specific genes could, therefore,
19 provide an erect canopy while minimising negative pleiotropic effects. In the BR biosynthesis
20 pathway, *DWARF1/DIMINUTO* (*DWF1/DIM*) encodes a C-24 reductase that catalyses the
21 production of the first committed sterol BR precursor, while *DWF4* and *DWF11* encode 22 α -
22 hydroxylase enzymes that act later in the pathway, and which exhibit partial functional
23 redundancy.

24 **Results:** Using ethyl-methanesulfonate (EMS)-induced mutations that introduce premature
25 stop codons, we generated wheat lines lacking functional copies of all three homoeologues of
26 *DWF1* and *DWF4* in the Cadenza background. The *dwf4-abd* mutant displayed upright leaves
27 and a slight height reduction but showed no differences in grain size or weight when tested in
28 glasshouse and field conditions. The *dwf1-abd* mutant also produced an upright canopy, but
29 tiller number, grain size and grain weight were reduced compared to the wild-type.

30 Scanning electron microscopy revealed that the reduced leaf angle in these mutants was due to
31 reduced cell elongation in the auricle region of the lamina joint, causing the leaf blade to be
32 more tightly packed around the ligule. The *dwf1-abd* mutant was hypersensitive to exogenous
33 BR application. Metabolite profiling showed that concentrations of the BR precursors
34 campesterol (CR), campestanol (CN) and 6-oxoCN were significantly reduced in *dwf1-abd*
35 seedlings compared to wild-type controls, whereas levels of the bioactive BRs castasterone
36 (CS) and brassinolide (BL) were unexpectedly elevated in both *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd*.

37 **Conclusion:** Wheat *dwf4* null mutations confer an erect canopy architecture without yield
38 penalties, suggesting this gene may be a promising target to develop ideotypes suitable for
39 high-density planting. By contrast, *dwf1* null mutants exhibit negative pleiotropic effects and
40 are unlikely to be useful for agriculture. The characterised mutants advance our understanding
41 of BR metabolism and can be explored for their potential to improve grain yields.

42 **Keywords:** wheat, brassinosteroids, leaf angle, ligule, plant height, grain size.

43

44

45 **Background**

46 Brassinosteroids (BRs) are plant hormones that regulate several traits of direct agronomic
47 value, such as stem elongation, leaf angle, and grain size [1, 2]. By promoting cell elongation
48 in the stem, BRs affect overall plant height, and by regulating cell elongation and proliferation
49 in the auricle region of the lamina joint, they influence leaf angle [3]. Because these traits
50 contribute to crop architecture and yield potential, there is interest in studying natural and
51 induced genetic variation that alters BR biosynthesis and signalling. Characterising this
52 variation can help breed crop varieties with optimal stature, canopy structure and grain
53 production.

54 Mutations that reduce BR biosynthesis or signalling affect lamina joint development leading
55 to altered leaf angles in cereals such as rice (*Oryza sativa*), maize (*Zea mays*), and barley
56 (*Hordeum vulgare*) [2]. However, BR-deficient and BR-insensitive plants also exhibit negative
57 pleiotropic effects, such as reduced fertility and grain size, which limits their usefulness for
58 wheat breeding [4-6]. By contrast, alleles that confer targeted or partial suppression of BR
59 signalling can lead to enhanced cereal yields. For example, loss of a wheat (*Triticum aestivum*
60 L.) haploblock including *ZnF-B*, which encodes a RING-type E3 ligase that targets a BR-
61 signalling repressor, confers a moderate reduction in BR signalling, resulting in a compact,
62 upright canopy and higher grain yields without negative pleiotropic effects [7]. Similarly, rice
63 lines carrying a mutation that activates the BR catabolic gene *BR-DEFICIENT DWARF3*
64 (*BRD3*) specifically in developing panicles exhibit reduced BR signalling in these tissues,
65 resulting in increased panicle branching and grain number without negative effects on grain
66 size [8].

67 Another approach to modify BR levels is to target genes encoding BR biosynthesis enzymes.
68 *DWARF1/DIMINUTO (DWF1/DIM)* encodes a C-24 reductase that converts 24-
69 methylenecholesterol (24-MC) to campesterol (CR), the committed sterol precursor of BRs as
70 shown in Figure 1 [9,10]. This protein contains an N-terminal transmembrane domain and a
71 flavin adenine dinucleotide-binding (FAD) domain, which is common in oxidoreductase
72 enzymes and essential for its normal function [10]. Because DWF1 is the only enzyme
73 catalysing this reaction, *dwf1* loss-of-function alleles exhibit severe reductions in BR levels. In
74 *Arabidopsis (Arabidopsis thaliana)*, *dwf1* null mutants are BR-deficient and exhibit extremely
75 short hypocotyls, stems, petioles, and roots due to reduced longitudinal cell elongation [9, 11].

76 Loss-of-function mutations in orthologous *DWF1*/*DIM* genes in barley, rice, and maize also
 77 confer erect leaves, semi-dwarf stature, reduced root elongation, shortened grains, and reduced
 78 fertility [5, 12, 13].

79 By contrast, the 22 α -hydroxylation of campestanol (CN) to 6-deoxocathasterone (6-deoxoCT)
 80 and of 6-oxoCN to cathasterone (CT), rate-limiting steps in the BR biosynthesis pathway [14],
 81 are catalysed by two cytochrome P450 monooxygenases in cereals: *DWARF4*
 82 (*DWF4*/*CYP90B2*) and *DWF11* (*CYP724B1*) as shown in Figure 1 [14]. Both enzymes
 83 contain conserved heme-, dioxygen- and steroid-binding domains that are essential for
 84 enzymatic activity [15,16]. This differs from *Arabidopsis*, where these steps are catalysed only
 85 by *DWF4* [17].

86
 87 **Figure 1: Simplified BR biosynthesis pathway leading to production of BL.** The enzymes
 88 catalysing each reaction are shown for each step.

89 In rice, *DWF4* and *DWF11* have partially redundant functions, providing the opportunity for
 90 more targeted reduction in BR activity [14]. *OsDWF4* transcript levels are highest in leaf blades
 91 and the *osdwf4-1* mutant exhibits an erect-leaf canopy and only a slight reduction in final height
 92 with no effects on reproductive development [14]. By contrast, *OsDWF11* is expressed more
 93 broadly, including in vegetative meristems, and the *osdwf11* mutant has a semi-dwarf stature
 94 with shorter grains and compact panicles [14, 18]. The phenotype of the *osdwf4/osdwf11*

95 double mutant is more extreme, including severe dwarfism and malformed leaves [14].
96 Therefore, the functional redundancy and distinct expression profiles of *DWF4* and *DWF11*
97 allow for the selection of *dwf4* alleles that confer a desirable erect leaf architecture without the
98 negative pleiotropic effects associated with BR-deficient mutants [14]. This was also
99 demonstrated in maize where loss-of-function *ZmDWF4* alleles confer improved
100 photosynthetic capacity, reduced shade avoidance response and higher yields in densely sown
101 plots [19].

102 The wheat genome contains homoeologous triads of *DWF1* on homoeologous group 7
103 chromosomes, of *DWF11* on homoeologous group 2 chromosomes, and of *DWF4* on
104 homoeologous group 4 chromosomes [20]. In addition, an inter-chromosomal duplication
105 event specific to wheat originated four *DWF4*-like genes on homoeologous group 3
106 chromosomes, but these genes are expressed at very low levels, suggesting they play a minor
107 role in BR biosynthesis [20]. To date, genetic variation in BR biosynthesis genes has not been
108 widely exploited in wheat breeding programmes, potentially because the functional
109 redundancy of its hexaploid genome masks the effects of individual gene mutations.

110 The goal of the current study was to characterise the physiological function of *DWF1* and
111 *DWF4* in bread wheat and determine whether variation in these genes could confer agronomic
112 benefits. Plants carrying loss-of-function mutations in all homoeologous copies of either *DWF1*
113 or *DWF4* exhibited an upright canopy architecture due to anatomical differences in the lamina
114 joint. The *dwf1-abd* mutants were also shorter and produced smaller and lighter grains than the
115 wild-type. By contrast, *dwf4-abd* mutants showed only a slight height reduction and maintained
116 normal grain size, suggesting that *DWF4* is a promising breeding target to develop varieties
117 suitable for dense planting regimes.

118 **Materials and methods**

119 **Plant materials and growth conditions**

120 **Plant materials**

121 The spring bread wheat cultivar Cadenza, supplied by CPB Twyford Ltd, was used in all
122 experiments. Lines carrying ethyl methanesulphonate (EMS)-induced point mutations in
123 *DWF1-A*, *DWF1-B*, *DWF1-D*, *DWF4-A*, *DWF4-B* and *DWF4-D* were identified from an online
124 database (http://plants.ensembl.org/Triticum_aestivum/). DNA from M₂ lines was subjected to
125 exon capture and sequencing to identify mutations [21]. M₃ seed was grown at the John Innes

126 Centre, who generated and supplied the M₄ seed. Each M₄ line was inter-crossed to combine
127 mutations, and F₁ plants (AaBbDd) were backcrossed twice to non-mutagenized Cadenza to
128 reduce background mutations, then selfed to obtain a BC₂F₂ population segregating for each
129 mutation. We selected all single (*tadwfl1-a*, *tadwfl1-b*, *tadwfl1-d*, *tadwfl4-a*, *tadwfl4-b* and *tadwfl4-*
130 *d*), double (*tadwfl1-ab*, *tadwfl1-ad*, *tadwfl1-bd*, *tadwfl4-ab*, *tadwfl4-ad* and *tadwfl4-bd*) and triple
131 (*tadwfl1-abd* and *tadwfl4-abd*) mutant combinations, as well as the wild-type null segregant line
132 (*TaDWF1-NS* and *TaDWF4-NS*) from this population for phenotypic characterisation.

133 **Genotyping**

134 Genomic DNA was extracted from seedling tissue using a CTAB-buffer extraction [22]. *DWF1*
135 and *DWF4* genes were amplified to check for the presence of each mutation using 0.05 μM of
136 homoeologue-specific PCR primers (Additional file 1, Table S1) with Hot Shot Diamond
137 Mastermix (Clontech Life Science, Stourbridge, UK) and annealing temperature between 55-65
138 °C (Additional file 1, Table S1). PCR amplicons were purified using QIAquick PCR
139 Purification kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and sequenced by Eurofins Genomics
140 (Wolverhampton, UK).

141 *dwfl1* and *dwf4* mutations were selected by KASP assays using KASP low-ROX Mastermix
142 (LGC, Teddington, UK) with primers specific to each SNP with FAM, HEX or VIC tails and
143 a common reverse primer with 37 cycles of touchdown PCR (Additional file 1, Table S2).
144 Plates were read using the 7500 Fast Software v2.3 (Applied Biosystems, Foster City,
145 California, USA) and analysed using the KlusterCaller™ software (LGC, Teddington, UK).

146 **Phenotypic characterisation of *dwfl1* and *dwf4* mutants under glasshouse conditions**

147 Preliminary phenotyping of all *dwfl1* and *dwf4* combinatorial mutants was performed under
148 glasshouse conditions (18-20 °C day/14-15 °C night temperatures, 16 h photoperiod) using four
149 biological replicates, organized in a randomized complete block design. More detailed
150 phenotyping of *dwfl1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants used six biological replicates, also sown in a
151 randomised complete block design. Wheat grains were imbibed on damp filter paper at 4 °C
152 for 4-5 d, then transferred to 15 cm pots containing 75% peat, 12% sterilised loam, 3%
153 vermiculite and 10% grit.

154 Leaf angle was defined as the angle between the vertical stem and the midrib. Measurements
155 were made using a protractor for the 2nd leaf at the seedling stage (GS12) and the flag leaf at
156 anthesis (GS61) and at 14 days post-anthesis (DPA) (GS73) on a representative primary shoot.

157 Final plant height was measured from the soil surface to the tip of the spike of the tallest shoot
158 at maturity (GS97). Internode and spike lengths (from the base of the first spikelet to the top
159 of the terminal spikelet, just beneath the awns) were measured from the 3 tallest shoots per
160 plant. The number of fertile spikelets per spike was measured from 2-3 spikes per plant. Grain
161 area was determined using a Marvin grain analyser (INDOSAW, India) with 3-5 g of clean
162 threshed grain. Thousand Grain Weight (TGW) was measured by weighing 1,000 clean
163 threshed grains.

164 **Field assessment of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants**

165 The genotypes *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd* and Cadenza were sown in April 2022 at Rothamsted
166 Research Experimental farm in 1 m² plots as a randomized complete block design with four
167 replicates. All experiments were grown with standard farm practice for fertiliser and pesticides,
168 but no plant growth regulators were applied. Final plant height, spike length, number of
169 spikelets per spike, grain area, and TGW were measured as in the glasshouse experiment using
170 10-15 plants per plot. Flag leaf angle (FLA) was measured using a protractor on 10-15 uniform
171 tillers at anthesis. Final plant height was recorded as the mean of the 10 tallest fertile shoots
172 per plot.

173 **High throughput phenotyping under the Field Scanalyzer**

174 For seed multiplication, *dwf1-abd* and Cadenza were sown in 1 m² plots in Rothamsted
175 Research Experimental Farm in spring 2019. The row-to-row spacing was 20 cm, and plant-
176 to-plant spacing was 10 cm with a density of 60 plants/ m² plot. These genotypes were sown
177 in autumn 2020 under the Field Scanalyzer, located in Rothamsted Research Experimental
178 Farm. Three biological replicates of both genotypes were grown in 0.6 m² plots as a randomised
179 complete block design. Data were captured using the red, green and blue (RGB) camera and
180 the 3D laser scanners from seedling establishment to harvesting [23]. RGB images were used
181 to calculate the canopy cover (ratio of green pixels to the total amount of pixels within the
182 image) [24] and to quantify the number of spikes per image, then converted to spike density
183 (spikes/m²) [25]. The 3D point clouds collected by the 3D laser scanners were processed to
184 measure the canopy height using methods described previously [26].

185 **Brassinosteroid analysis**

186 Bioactive and precursor BR concentrations were measured in 2nd leaf seedling tissues of *dwf1-*
187 *abd*, *DWF1-NS*, *dwf4-abd*, *DWF4-NS*, and Cadenza. Multiple plants were pooled to obtain

188 sufficient tissue for each of four biological replicates. Leaf tissue was flash-frozen in liquid N₂
189 and freeze-dried. BRs were extracted, purified, and analysed by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS as
190 described previously [27].

191 **Lamina joint inclination assay**

192 Two-cm sections containing the 2nd leaf lamina joint, leaf sheath, and leaf blade were excised
193 from uniformly developed seedlings and floated in autoclaved water for 10 min in Petri dishes.
194 These sections were then transferred to Petri dishes containing either 10⁻⁵M epiBL (24-
195 *epibrassinolide*) solution or autoclaved water. The dishes were sealed with parafilm and
196 incubated at 29 °C in the dark for 2 d. Leaf angles were subsequently measured using a
197 protractor [28].

198 **Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for histological analysis**

199 Seedlings were grown in the glasshouse for 10-14 d under 16 h photoperiod. Leaf segments (~
200 1 cm long), including the second leaf lamina joints, were harvested and attached to aluminium
201 stubs using a 50:50 mixture of graphite and TissueTek. Samples were immediately immersed
202 in liquid nitrogen, then transferred to a GATAN ALTO 2100 cryo-prep system, sputtered with
203 argon and coated with a thin layer of gold. Micrographs were captured using a JEOL JSM-
204 6360LV scanning electron microscope and cell lengths were measured using ImageJ 1.48v
205 software [29].

206 **Statistical analysis**

207 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted on the glasshouse data using Genstat software
208 (Release 21.1) to estimate statistical differences between genotypes and treatments, from which
209 *p* values, standard errors of the difference of the means (SED), and least significant differences
210 (LSD) at the 5% level were calculated. Field data were analysed using unbalanced ANOVA
211 with regression. Differences between genotypes were further tested using Fisher's LSD
212 unprotected test, providing *p* values. Paired Student's *t*-tests which provided *p* values, were
213 performed in GraphPad Prism software (version 9.4.0) to compare means in phenotyping data
214 from the Field Scanalyzer. Two-way ANOVA and F-test were performed in R (R version 4.4.1)
215 to test the sensitivity and interaction of genotypes to epiBL treatment, respectively. The
216 significance level was set to 0.05. Mean and residual plots were generated for each dataset to
217 assess normality. Graphs were made with GraphPad Prism (version 9.4.0).

218

219 Results

220 Generation of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants

221 We generated *dwf1* and *dwf4* knockout mutants in wheat by identifying EMS-induced point
222 mutations that introduce premature stop codons in each of the three respective homoeologues
223 (Table 1, Additional file 1, Figure S1). The *dwf1* mutant alleles each encode truncated proteins
224 lacking either the FAD or transmembrane domains (Additional file 1, Figure S1A, B).
225 Similarly, the *dwf4* mutant alleles encode proteins lacking conserved domains, including the
226 heme-binding domain, that are required for function (Additional file 1, Figure S1C, D). We
227 selected single, double, and triple mutant lines for both *DWF1* and *DWF4*, as well as their wild-
228 type null segregants, for phenotypic characterisation.

229 **Table 1:** *DWF1* and *DWF4* homoeologues and mutant alleles used in this study. The position
230 of mutations introducing premature stop codons (*) are indicated.

Gene	Gene ID	Mutant name	Amino acid substitution	Cadenza TILLING line
<i>DWF1-A</i>	<i>TraesCS7A02G559400</i>	<i>dwf1-a</i>	W92*	381
<i>DWF1-B</i>	<i>TraesCS7B02G484200</i>	<i>dwf1-b</i>	Q23*	1444
<i>DWF1-D</i>	<i>TraesCS7D02G550700</i>	<i>dwf1-d</i>	Q252*	1339
<i>DWF4-A</i>	<i>TraesCS4A02G078000</i>	<i>dwf4-a</i>	W168*	1353
<i>DWF4-B</i>	<i>TraesCS4B02G234100</i>	<i>dwf4-b</i>	W39*	12
<i>DWF4-D</i>	<i>TraesCS4D02G235200</i>	<i>dwf4-d</i>	W352*	934

231

232 Phenotypic characterization of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under glasshouse 233 conditions

234 To characterize *DWF1* and *DWF4* function in wheat, we measured plant height and FLA in
235 single, double, and triple knockout mutants. We observed mild, but significant reductions in
236 FLA in all single and double knockout *dwf1* mutants compared to *DWF1-NS*, except *dwf1-ab*
237 (Additional file 1, Figure S2). The reduction in FLA was much greater in the triple *dwf1-abd*
238 mutant (Additional file 1, Figure S2). Height was unaffected in any single or double *dwf1*
239 mutant but was significantly reduced in the *dwf1-abd* mutant (Additional file 1, Figure S2). All
240 single and double *dwf4* mutations also exhibited reduced FLA compared to *DWF4-NS* although
241 the difference was significant only for *dwf4-bd* (Additional file 1, Figure S2). As for *dwf1-abd*,

242 FLA was significantly reduced in the *dwf4-abd* triple mutant. In contrast, plant height was
243 unaffected in all single, double and triple *dwf4* mutants (Additional file 1, Figure S2).

244 Because of the major reduction in FLA in *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants, we performed a
245 more detailed phenotypic characterization of these lines, along with their respective null
246 segregant lines (*DWF1-NS* and *DWF4-NS*) and Cadenza. The gross morphology of these lines
247 at the hard dough stage (GS87) and maturity (GS97) is shown in Figures 2A and 2C,
248 respectively. Leaf angle was significantly reduced at the 2nd leaf and flag leaf stages in both
249 *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants compared with their respective null segregant controls
250 (Figures 2A, 2B, 3A, and 3B). The reduction was greater in *dwf1-abd* than in *dwf4-abd* at the
251 2nd leaf seedling stage, while at the flag leaf stage the leaf angles in these mutants were similar
252 and significantly reduced relative to their respective null segregants. This result suggests that
253 similar regulatory mechanisms control leaf angle at both the seedling and reproductive stages.

254 Both *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* seedlings were significantly shorter than their respective null
255 segregant controls (Figure 3C). However, only *dwf1-abd* showed a significant reduction in final
256 plant height (Figure 2C and 3D), due to decreases in the length of the spike and the upper four
257 internodes (Figure 3E, and 3F). In addition, *dwf1-abd* produced fewer spikelets per spike,
258 smaller and lighter grains, and fewer tillers per plant compared to *DWF1-NS*, whereas *dwf4-*
259 *abd* did not significantly differ from *DWF4-NS* for these traits (Figures 2D, 2E and 3G-3J).

260

261 **Figure 2: Phenotype of *dwf1* and *dwf4* triple mutants.** (A) *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd*, respective
 262 null segregant lines and Cadenza photographed at the hard dough stage (GS87) (Bar length =
 263 20 cm). (B) Flag leaf and main stem indicating leaf angles at GS87 (Bar length = 3 cm). (C)
 264 Mature plants and (D) spikes of *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd*, *DWF1-NS*, *DWF4-NS* and Cadenza at
 265 GS97. Bar lengths are 30 cm and 3 cm, respectively. (E) Ten grains end-to-end and side-by-
 266 side of *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd* and Cadenza at maturity (Bar length = 2 cm).

267

268 **Figure 3: Phenotypic characterization of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under glasshouse**
 269 **conditions.** (A) Leaf angle at 2nd leaf seedling stage, GS11 (n ~ 20). (B) Flag leaf angles (FLA)
 270 at 14 days post-anthesis, GS73 (n = 6). (C) Height at 2nd leaf stage (n ~ 20). (D) Final plant
 271 height and (E) internode lengths of mature stems (n = 6). (F) Spike length at maturity (n = 6).
 272 (G) Number of spikelets per spike (n = 6). (H) Area and (I) TGW of mature grains (n = 6). (J)
 273 Number of tillers per plant (n = 6). Different letters indicate significant differences between
 274 genotypes (obtained from Fisher's unprotected LSD test). p values $*0.05 > p > 0.01$,
 275 $**0.01 > p > 0.001$, $***0.0001 > p > 0.00001$ (obtained from Fisher's unprotected LSD test).

276

277 ***dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants display anatomical differences in the lamina joint**

278 We used scanning electron microscopy to investigate anatomical differences around the auricle
279 (Figure 4A) and adaxial lamina joint regions of the 2nd leaf. Both *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd*
280 exhibited significantly shorter average cell lengths ($p < 0.0001$) in the auricle compared to
281 Cadenza (Figures 4B and 4C). In addition, the leaf blade was more tightly packed around the
282 ligule in both mutants than in Cadenza (Figure 4D).

283

284 **Figure 4: Scanning electron microscopy imaging around the lamina joint in the *dwf1* and**
285 ***dwf4* mutants and Cadenza.** (A) The leaf segments containing the lamina joint of the 2nd leaf
286 in *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd*, and Cadenza (Bar length = 1 cm). The auricle region is smaller in both
287 mutants compared to Cadenza as shown by arrows. (B) Images taken around the auricle region
288 of the lamina joint (Magnification = 130X, scale bar = 100 μm). (C) Cell length from images

289 of *dwf1-abd* (n = 197), *dwf4-abd* (n = 200) and Cadenza (n = 131). Different letters indicate
290 significant differences between the genotypes obtained from Fisher's LSD unprotected test.
291 (D) Imaging around the adaxial side of the lamina joint. (Left image, magnification = 30X,
292 scale bar = 500 μ m; right image magnification = 120X, scale bar = 200 μ m).

293 **Response of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants to BR application**

294 To test the sensitivity of *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants to exogenous BRs, we applied epiBL
295 to seedling sections of the mutants, their respective null segregants and Cadenza and measured
296 leaf angles in lamina joint inclination assays. While all lines responded to the treatment with
297 an increase in leaf angle, there was a significant interaction between treatment and genotype,
298 with *dwf1-abd* responding much more strongly to 10^{-5} M epiBL compared to the other lines
299 ($F_{4,111} = 28.892, p < 0.001$) (Figure 5).

300

301 **Figure 5: Response of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants to external BR application.** Lamina joint
302 inclination assays were performed on *dwf1-abd*, *DWF1-NS*, *dwf4-abd*, *DWF4-NS* and Cadenza.
303 Leaf angles of the 2nd leaf at seedling stage (n = 14) were measured after treatment with 10^{-5} M
304 epiBL or water. The data were analysed using two-way ANOVA, where an F-test was used to
305 test for the interaction.

306 **Analysis of endogenous BR levels in *dwf1* and *dwf4* triple mutants**

307 We detected ten BRs in seedling tissues of *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants. In *dwf1-abd*, the
308 early sterol intermediates CR, campestanol (CN) and 6-oxoCN levels were reduced by 126-
309 fold, 12.8-fold, and 3.7-fold, respectively, compared to *DWF1-NS* (Figure 6, Additional file 1,
310 Table S3). Unexpectedly, the concentration of the bioactive BRs castasterone (CS) and
311 brassinolide (BL) were significantly higher in *dwf1-abd* than in *DWF1-NS*, potentially

312 reflecting changes in activity in other branches of the BR biosynthetic pathway. The
 313 concentration of CN, the substrate for DWF4 and DWF11, did not differ significantly between
 314 *dwf4-abd* and *DWF4-NS* (Figure 6). Moreover, 6-deoxoCT, the immediate product of these
 315 enzymes, as well as 6-deoxytyphasterol (6-deoxoTY), accumulated to significantly higher
 316 levels in *dwf4-abd* than in *DWF4-NS*. However, the concentrations of both compounds were
 317 significantly lower in *DWF4-NS* than in *DWF1-NS* or Cadenza. The concentration of bioactive
 318 BL was also significantly higher in *dwf4-abd* than in *DWF4-NS* (Figure 6).

319

320 **Figure 6: BR levels in *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants.** The concentrations of BRs (pg/mg DW)
 321 namely CR (campesterol), CN (campestanol), 6-oxoCN, 6-deoxoCT (6-deoxocathasterone),
 322 TY (typhasterol), 6-deoxoTY, CS (castasterone), BL, epiCS (24-epicastasterone) and DS
 323 (dolichosterone) were determined in seedlings of the *dwf1-abd*, *dwf4-abd* mutants, *DWF1-NS*,
 324 *DWF4-NS* and Cadenza. Mean values from five biological replicates are recorded. Statistically
 325 significant differences from the respective *NS* control are denoted by * $0.05 > p > 0.01$, ** 0.01
 326 $> p > 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$ (obtained by pairwise Student's *t*-test).

327

328 High-throughput phenotyping of the *dwf1* mutant using a Field Scalyzer

329 When multiplying *dwf1-abd* seed in field plots in 2019, we noted obvious reductions in height
 330 and canopy cover compared to Cadenza (Additional file 1, Figure S3). To investigate canopy
 331 cover, spike density, and stem elongation patterns throughout the growing season, we grew
 332 *dwf1-abd* alongside Cadenza under the Field Scalyzer in winter 2020. From early November
 333 2020 to late July 2021, *dwf1-abd* consistently exhibited lower canopy cover than Cadenza,
 334 including during flowering (Figures 7A, 7B and Additional file 1, Figure S4). The *dwf1-abd*
 335 plants were shorter than Cadenza throughout the reproductive stage (Figure 7C), with height
 336 reductions of ~30% at GS65 and ~25% at GS91 (Figure 7D). In addition, spike density at GS69
 337 was significantly lower in *dwf1-abd* compared to Cadenza (Figure 7E and Additional file 1,
 338 Figure S4).

339

340 **Figure 7: High throughput phenotyping of *dwf1* mutant under a Field Scalyzer.** (A)
 341 Canopy cover was estimated from these RGB images throughout the life cycle of the crop (B)
 342 and specifically at flowering stages GS59 (spike emergence), GS65 (flowering halfway), and
 343 GS69 (flowering complete) (n = 3). Significant differences were denoted as * $p < 0.05$ from
 344 the one-tailed Student's *t*-test. (C) Plant height was recorded in *dwf1-abd* and Cadenza from
 345 mid-May 2021 (initiation of internode elongation) to August 2021 (maturity). (D) Heights of
 346 these genotypes at the GS65 and GS97 (maturity) ** $p < 0.01$ (obtained from one-tailed
 347 Student's *t*-test). (E) RGB images were used to estimate spike density (number of spikes per
 348 m²) in *dwf1-abd* and Cadenza (n = 3). ** $p < 0.01$ (obtained from one-tailed Student's *t*-test).

349 **Phenotypic characterization of *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under field**
 350 **conditions**

351 We compared the *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants with Cadenza in a full, replicated field
 352 experiment sown in spring 2022. Both mutants exhibited significantly reduced FLAs compared
 353 to Cadenza (Figure 8A). The *dwf1-abd* mutant was ~50% shorter than Cadenza due to
 354 significant reductions in the lengths of the spike, peduncle, P-1 and P-2 internodes (Figure 8B-
 355 8D). The reduction in height in *dwf1-abd* was approximately double the difference observed in
 356 the earlier winter-sown experiment (Figure 7C and 7D), suggesting that environmental
 357 conditions impact the expression of these traits. Grain area and TGW were also significantly
 358 lower in *dwf1-abd* compared to Cadenza (Figure 8E and 8F).

359 The *dwf4-abd* mutant was also significantly shorter than Cadenza (14% reduction), a milder
 360 effect than in the *dwf1-abd* mutant (Figure 8B) and only the peduncle and spike were
 361 significantly shorter (Figure 8C and 8D). Grain size and TGW did not differ from Cadenza
 362 (Figure 8E and 8F).

363 Taken together, the *dwf1-abd* mutant displayed compact architecture with smaller, lighter
 364 grains, whereas the *dwf4-abd* mutant exhibited an erect leaf canopy and a mild height reduction
 365 without any detrimental changes in grain characteristics.

366

367 **Figure 8: Phenotypic characterization of *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants in the field**
368 **during 2022.** (A) Flag leaf angle at anthesis (n ~ 40). (B) Final plant height, (C) Internode
369 lengths and (D) spike lengths at maturity (n = 55-60). (E) Grain area and (F) TGW of mature
370 grains (n = 4). Different letters indicate significant differences amongst the genotypes (obtained
371 from Fisher's unprotected LSD test). p values $***0.001 > p > 0.0001$, $****0.0001 > p > 0.00001$
372 (obtained from Fisher's unprotected LSD test).

373 **Discussion**

374 ***DWF1* is required for normal above-ground architecture in wheat**

375 The *dwf1-abd* triple mutant displayed striking developmental defects under both glasshouse
376 and field conditions, including a ~50% reduction in height due to restricted internode
377 elongation, erect leaves, and a compact spike. Grain size and weight were also significantly
378 lower than the wild-type. Similar phenotypes have been reported for *DWF1* knockouts in rice,
379 barley, and maize, demonstrating a conserved role in promoting stem elongation and grain
380 filling [5, 12, 13].

381 High-throughput canopy imaging using Rothamsted's Field Scanalyzer revealed that green
382 canopy cover was significantly reduced in *dwf1-abd* plots compared to Cadenza throughout the
383 growing season (Figure 7). While it is not possible to exclude the effect of different germination
384 rates, which was not recorded in this experiment, the lower canopy cover for the *dwf1-abd* plots
385 is likely due to its more erect phenotype [12, 13]. This is also supported by the lower spike
386 density at GS69 of *dwf1-abd* plots compared to Cadenza, indicating a lower number of fertile
387 tillers contributing to lower canopy cover. This is consistent with studies in rice showing that
388 BR signalling stimulates axillary bud outgrowth, promoting tillering [30]. Taken together, the
389 combination of reduced height, lower tillering and smaller grains means that *dwf1* mutations
390 are unlikely to be beneficial in wheat breeding.

391 The *dwf1-abd* mutant was hypersensitive to exogenous BL, and the concentrations of CR, the
392 immediate product of DWF1, were 126-fold lower than in wild-type control plants, consistent
393 with BR-deficiency [9, 31] (Figure 6). The concentrations of downstream intermediates were
394 also reduced in this mutant, consistent with results from *dwf1* mutants in rice and Arabidopsis
395 [9, 10, 12]. However, the levels of bioactive BRs, CS and BL, were significantly increased in
396 the *dwf1-abd* triple mutant compared to the null segregant (Figure 6). This suggests an
397 alternative biosynthetic route for BL and CS and possible spatial specificity in BR distribution.

398 In the rice *br-deficient dwarf2 (brd2)* mutant, defective in the *DWF1/DIM* gene, the production
399 of DS, a bioactive BR, has been suggested as an explanation for its mild BR-deficient
400 phenotype [12]. However, the wheat *dwf1-abd* mutant does not contain elevated DS levels
401 compared to *DWF1-NS*, so it remains unclear which pathway leads to BL and CS. Tissue-
402 specific regulation of BR biosynthesis during wheat seedling development may be involved,
403 which could be tested by conducting a more detailed spatial and temporal analysis of BR levels
404 in the *dwf1-abd* mutant.

405 ***DWF4* alters canopy architecture with no negative pleiotropic effects on grain** 406 **development**

407 The *dwf4-abd* mutant exhibited significantly reduced FLA at anthesis and produced compact
408 spikes with a mild reduction in plant height in the field. Grain size and TGW were unaffected,
409 consistent with the low expression of *DWF4* in developing grains (Additional file 1, Figure S6)
410 [32]. This organ-specific effect is consistent with earlier studies in rice, where *DWF4* knockout
411 mutants exhibit modified leaf angle without affecting height or grain traits [14]. Our results
412 suggest that *DWF4* may be a promising target for breeding wheat ideotypes that are suited for
413 high-density planting. Although *dwf4* did not produce an increase in TGW compared with
414 Cadenza in the field experiment, it is likely that it will enable higher yields than the control at
415 high planting densities. In maize, *lac1*, a *zmdwf4* null mutant, maintains photosynthetic
416 efficiency at high planting densities in contrast to the wild-type, allowing higher yields [19].

417 Scanning electron microscopy of the adaxial and auricle/collar region of the lamina joint
418 indicated that the leaf blade was more tightly packed around the ligule in *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-*
419 *abd* than in Cadenza. This phenotype resembles the wheat *compact plant architecture (cpa)*
420 mutant, in which a loss-of-function mutation in *TaSPL8* downregulates genes in the BR and
421 auxin signalling pathways [33]. Additionally, both *dwf1* and *dwf4* exhibited significantly
422 reduced cell lengths in the auricle region, likely limiting longitudinal elongation and preventing
423 leaves from bending away from the stem. This feature is commonly reported in erect-statured
424 rice and maize BR-related mutants [6, 34-36].

425 Exogenous BL restored seedling leaf angle in *dwf4-abd*, demonstrating that *DWF4* contributes
426 to endogenous BR biosynthesis, controlling leaf inclination [17]. However, BR levels in *dwf4-*
427 *abd* seedlings did not differ from the controls, which was also observed in rice, where the levels
428 of BR intermediates were altered in the *osdwf4-1/osdwf11-4* double mutant but not in either
429 single mutant [14]. This discrepancy may be due to the tissue-specific expression of *DWF4*

430 within the lamina joint, which was not captured in our whole-seedling analysis. Supporting this
431 possibility, the maize *lac1* mutant exhibits reduced levels of 6-deoxoCT and CS specifically in
432 the ligule region [19]. Therefore, a more detailed spatial and temporal analysis of BR
433 metabolites in wheat lamina joints will be required to determine whether similar localized
434 variation in BR distribution determines the erect-leaf phenotype of *dwf4-abd*.

435 **Conclusions**

436 Loss-of-function mutations in *DWF1* and *DWF4* both confer an upright canopy architecture in
437 wheat. However, because *DWF1* is the only enzyme catalysing the conversion of 24-MC to CR
438 early in the BR biosynthesis pathway, null mutations also cause reductions in height, tiller
439 number and grain size, pleiotropic effects that will likely restrict the utility of *dwf1* loss-of-
440 function alleles for crop improvement. By contrast, *dwf4* null alleles confer erect-leaf
441 architecture with only a mild reduction in height and no effect on grain development.
442 Therefore, introducing natural or induced allelic variation in *DWF4* is a promising strategy to
443 breed wheat ideotypes suited to high-density planting conditions.

444 **Declarations**

445 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

446 Not applicable

447 **Consent for publication**

448 Not applicable

449 **Availability of data and materials**

450 All data generated in this study are provided in the manuscript and additional file 1. Biological
451 materials are available upon request from Stephen Pearce.

452 **Competing interests**

453 Authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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463 **Author contribution**

464 SGT, PH, MSG, JF, and ALP designed the experiments. MSG and SGT developed wheat *dwf1*
465 and *dwf4* mutants. MSG phenotyped the mutants and performed lamina joint inclination assays.
466 MSG prepared the tissue for BR analysis, which was performed by DT. NV performed the field
467 scanalyzer experiment and analysed the data. MSG and JA performed statistical analysis. PH,
468 MSG, and SP wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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569 **Short legends for supplementary data**

570 **Additional file 1**

571 **Figure S1:** *DWF1* and *DWF4* homoeologues and mutant alleles used in this study.

- 572 **Figure S2:** Phenotypic characterization of all combinatorial *dwf1* and *dwf4* mutants under
573 glasshouse conditions.
- 574 **Figure S3:** Phenotype of Cadenza and *dwf1-abd* mutant at the tillering stage in the field.
- 575 **Figure S4:** High throughput phenotyping of *dwf1-abd* mutant under Field Scanalyzer.
- 576 **Figure S5:** Expression of *DWF1* genes in wheat variety ‘Azhurnaya’.
- 577 **Figure S6:** Expression of *DWF4* and *DWF11* genes in wheat variety ‘Azhurnaya’.
- 578 **Table S1:** Homoeologue-specific primers designed to amplify fragments around the
579 deleterious mutations in *TaDWF1* and *TaDWF4* genes.
- 580 **Table S2:** KASP primers designed to differentiate the mutant and wild type allele in
581 segregating *DWF1* and *DWF4* populations.
- 582 **Table S3:** BR levels (pg/mg DW) in *dwf1-abd* and *dwf4-abd* mutants and controls.

Supplementary Files

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